

Forms of Utilization of Forest Resources in Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

Study investigated the forms of utilization of forest resources in Southwestern, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was used in selecting rural dwellers used for this study while data were obtained from 340 respondents with the use of interview schedule. Descriptive statistical tools used were frequency counts, percentages and weighted mean score (WMS) to analysis the responses gotten from the field. Results revealed that more than half (54.4%) of the respondents were and a mean age of 51.1 years was recorded for the respondents; mean household size of 7 members, majority were literate with a mean of 10 years spent in school recorded for the respondents and a mean amount of ₦247,658.82 was recorded as income realized from forest resources utilization on a monthly basis. Respondents in the study area indicated they utilized various types of forest resources such as wild forest fruits, vegetables, medicinal plants, bush animal, forest trees, oil palm/coconut trees, water, sand and firewood. It was revealed that the utilized forest resources were utilized in various forms which include consumed at raw form, cooked form, agricultural inputs, asset formation, processed as herbs, medicine, for traditional rites, economic purposes and as source of energy. Deforestation, lack of extension contact to promote knowledge on use of the forest resources and lack of modern storage facilities were very severe constraints encountered in the utilization of forest resources in the study area. It was concluded that forest based rural people utilizes the available forest resources in the study area though through various form ranging from consumption, agricultural input, medicine, source of energy and for economic purpose amongst other several forms though the respondents encountered constraints in the utilization. It is therefore recommended that, there is a need for concerned agencies, stakeholders and governments to employ environmental extension specialists with competence in environmental resources to aid the promotion and increase the awareness of the people on various beneficial attributes to derive from the utilization of forests.

Key words: Forms, Utilization, Forest resources, Constraints

Introduction

Forest resources are key components of the natural resources base of any rural community, region, or country and they play a fundamental role in the socio-economic well-being of the people of these rural communities (Unongo *et al.*, 2019). This is particularly so in sub-Saharan Africa where most of the countries have a large rural population that depends on forest resources exploitation for their livelihood (Townson, 2012). According to Akinbile *et al.*, (2018), various kinds of wood and non-wood items are derived from the forest. Forest supplies many products in form of wood, which serves as basic material for construction, furniture, paper; and non-wood items, which include extracts such as the bark of medicinal trees, dye, fibre, gum, incense, latexes, oil resins, waxes, shellac and tannin compounds, food, bush meats, flowers, fruits, honey/nuts, leaves, seeds, spices as well as decorative, ceremonial and medicinal items. Forest contributes to poverty reduction and agricultural stability by protecting the soil and the majority of the rural communities that depend heavily on forest products for their livelihoods (Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism (MNRT), 2009). Forest is popularly known for the goods that they provide such as timbers, fuelwood, fodder, and other non-timber forest products which include soil, snail, *Agaricus bisporus*, wild vegetables, wild fruits amongst others (Ayanwuyi and Alamu, 2012). As cited in Olujobi (2015), forests are the major source of livelihood for many people particularly in developing countries, providing numerous benefits to human beings. These benefits may be direct (i.e provision of food and timber products) or indirectly through their services and contributions to the production process (i.e. protection of agricultural land), they may also be intangible (cultural values). Agbogidi and Eshegbeyi (2008) also maintained that forests play an important role in contributing to carbon sequestration and other global ecological services. Forest represents a point where ecological, economic, and social systems intersect

The importance of forests cannot be overemphasized, because they make numerous contributions directly and indirectly to the sustainable livelihood and well-being of billions of people across the world, through the provision of ecosystem services including environmental services such as wild food, fodder, fibre, wood, and medicine (Katerere *et al.*, 2009). Economic use of forests and their resources is an age-long practice among the majority of rural habitants as a source of livelihood and also a source of diversification of livelihood opportunity. Meanwhile, the use of the forest resources for economic purposes nowadays is not efficient enough which might be due to oversight by the rural people and non-awareness of the benefits the forest provides. The low level of the frequency of utilization of forest resources in the study area might not be unconnected with the limited knowledge about the types and various forms of utilization for forest resources. Therefore this study investigated the forms of utilization of forest resources in Southwestern Nigeria. The study describes the socio-economic characteristics of the rural habitants; identify the forest resources utilized; identify the forms at which the various forest resources are utilized and investigate the constraints to the utilization of forest resources in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Ondo, Osun and Oyo States from the Southwestern part of Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used for the study. First stage involved the purposive selection of two (2) agricultural zones that have proximity to forest vegetation in each of the state and this makes a total of six (6) agricultural zones used for this research work. Furthermore, random sampling technique was used to select three (3) extension blocks from each of the selected agricultural zones to make a total of eighteen (18) extension blocks used for this study. The fourth stage of sampling involved random selection of two extension cells from each of the randomly selected extension blocks. The selected cells in Ondo State includes Abusoro and Igodan from Okitipupa extension block; Bamikemo and Ojowo from Ileoluji/Okeigbo extension block; Asantan-Oju

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and Igbado from Ondo West extension block; Ipinsa and Olokuta from Akure South extension block; Isuada and Ogbese from Owo extension block, while Ebo and Eti-Oro were selected from Akoko South West extension block. From Osun State; Eti-Oni and Ikeji-Arakeji were selected from Oriade extension block; Aba Owode and Ilahun from Obokun extension block; Aba-Ijesha, and Idi-Obi from Ife South extension block; Wasinmi and Ayetoro from Irewole extension block; Idi-Iroko and Oloba from Iwo extension block while Asa-Ajagunlase and Asamu/Ilemowu were selected from Ola-Oluwa extension block. Lastly, in Oyo State, Onidoko 1 and Oni Gbodogi were selected from Oluyole extension block; Apata and Afeefu were selected from Ibarapa Central extension block; Ajofolowo and Gaa-Oro from Ibarapa North extension block; Bale Sagbo and Sagbo-Ile were selected from Iseyin extension block; Aba Sakin and Aba Ogun were selected from Atiba extension block; while Aba-Sakutu and Eleje were selected from Oyo West extension block. This makes a total of thirty-six (36) extension cells that were used for this research work. The extension cells were selected due to the presence of forest areas and rural populace engagement in forest-related economic activities in the area.

Random sampling was used to select 30% of respondents in each of the chosen thirty-six extension cells across the extension blocks. The total number of respondents interviewed in each of Ondo, Osun and Oyo State were 110, 91 and 139, respectively. Hence, a total of 340 respondents were used for this research work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

Table 1 reveals that more than half (54.4%) of the respondents were males while 45.6% were females. This result is an indication that male utilize the forest resources than the female counterpart in the southwestern part of Nigeria, though the male sex is slightly higher than the female counterparts hence, it could also be deduced that individuals that utilize forest resources in the Southwestern part of Nigeria were distributed between both sex. This is related to the fact that males probably have more financial responsibility to shoulder than their female counterpart in their respective communities. This result corroborates with the findings of Ayanwuyi (2013), where more than half (53.3%) of the forest users were males. In a similar vein, Wunder (2013) reported that generally, females had less access to credit and other necessary technologies required for forest resource exploitation/utilization. Thankur (2013) argued that some technologies used for forest resources collection required intensive labour which could not be handled by women. The table further revealed that 35.3% and 34.4% of the respondents were above 60 years of age and 41-50 years of age, while 13.2%, 9.1%, and 7.9% were between the ages of 51-60, not more than 30 years and between 31-40 years of age, respectively. The mean age of the respondents across the three states was 51.1 years. These findings show that rural dwellers that utilize forest resources in the study area were mature, energetic, economically active, which categorized them as individuals that are still ready to acquire more training that can aid improvement on their income. This finding is in line with those of Ayoade *et al.*, (2013); and Balogun and Obisesan (2014), who reported that their respondents were agile, active, and more innovative in the utilization of forest resources than the older ones and possessed more energy to be more productive. More than half (57.9%) of the respondents have 6-10 members in their household while 30.6% and 11.5% indicated not more than 5 and above 10 members in their households, respectively. The mean household size in the study area was 7 members. This result is an indication that Southwestern people have a fairly-large household size and this might be attributed to the dominance of arable

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crop production in the zone, which may have influenced the respondents to have more members in their household to shoulder the responsibility of farm labour to be used for agricultural activities. Above average (57.4%) of the respondents spent 7-12 years in school; 18.5% and 15.9% spent above 12 years and not more than 6 years in formal school, respectively, while only 8.2% do not have formal education. The mean years spent in school by the respondents was revealed to be 10 years. The importance of education and high literacy level is needed to optimally utilize the forest resources collected as this will have an impact on the form of utilization and the sustainable methods used to preserve the forest resources from going into extinction. More than half (56.5%) of the respondents were married, 21.8% were widows; 10.9% and 5.9% were single and divorced, respectively, while only 5.0% were separated. This result is an indication that respondents value the social institution in the study area through their adherence to the marriage institutions and this could influence the type and level of utilization of forest resources by the respective households. Furthermore, 45.3% of the respondents indicated not more than ₦100,000 as income realized per month; 23.8% and 19.1% indicated between ₦101,000-₦200,000 and above ₦300,000 monthly, respectively while 11.8% indicated between ₦201,000-₦300,000 as income realized monthly in the study area. The mean amount realized was ₦247,658.82. This result is an indication that respondents were averagely good income earners and this could be attributed to the extra income they realized from the utilization of forest resources. This result is not in consonance with the findings of Inoni (2009), who reported that most (77%) rural dwellers were low-income earners due to subsistence level of crop production, livestock production, forestry activities, and other agricultural activities. Lastly, 44.1% of the respondents indicated 21-30 years as the number of years accumulated in the collection of forest resources while 30.3%, 22.4%, and 3.2% indicated not more than 10 years, above 30 years, and between 11-20 years as the number of years accumulated in forest resources collection respectively in the study area. The mean years accumulated by the respondents were revealed to be 21.3 years. It is posited from this result that forest resources collectors are equipped with a wide horizon of experience to be dynamic and well-grounded in the forms and utilization of forest resources collected. This result is in line with the findings of Mbani (2015), where he had 20.74 years as the mean of the number of years of experience the respondents had in the collection of forest resources.

Forest Resources Utilized

Based on the result in Table 2, the respondents across the three States indicated the fruit forest resources they utilized out of the available forest resources in the study area. Majority (89.7%), 87.1% and 86.5% of the respondents indicated they utilized wild fruit resources which includes *Solanum aethiopicum* (igba), *Citrus aurantiifolia* and *Chrysophyllum albidum* (agbalumo) respectively while 85.3% of the respondents indicated *Persea americana* as forest fruit resources they utilize. Furthermore, forest fruit resources indicated by the respondents as utilized forest resources include *Juglans regia* (asala) which was indicated by 81.2% of the respondents; *Irvingia gabonensis* (oro) bush mango was indicated by 80.6% of the respondents; *Treculia africana* (African breadfruit) indicated by 75.9% of the respondents; *Cola acuminata* (obi) indicated by 74.7% of the respondents; *Garcinia kola* (orogbo) was indicated by 73.5% of the respondents and 70.6% of the respondents indicated *Psidium guajava* as wild fruits resources utilized in the study area. This result is an indication that the majority of the respondents still value the quality and the abundance of nature in providing their daily needs through the provisions from the forest.

In addition, 26.2% of the respondents indicated that they utilize *Cyperus esculentus* (ofi ho). The above-average representation of the respondents in utilizing *irvingiagabonensis* (oro) might be due to the dominance of the fruits in Oyo state and Osun state compared to its availability in Ondo state, hence it can be affirmed that *irvingiagabonensis* (oro) is a major wild fruits resources in Oyo and Osun state. Also, the minority (26.2%) of the respondents indicating the utilization of *Cyperus esculentus* (ofi ho) in the Southwest zone is connected to the fact that it is a scarce

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wild fruit forest resource found in the Southwest zone of Nigeria, rather it is a widely found and regenerated forest fruit resource in the Northern part of Nigeria.

Generally, this result affirmed that rural dwellers in the study area utilize forest fruit resources and this is an indication that the forest fruits resources have an impact on the livelihood of the rural dwellers in Southwest Nigeria. The utilized wild fruits resources were utilized in various forms such as eating in raw form; some were cooked like *Persea americana*, *Juglans regia* (asala) and *treculia africana* (African breadfruit). Also, the wild fruits were utilized for various purposes which include the sale of the wild fruits, consumed as food, snacks or purposely for medication purposes. This result is in line with the findings of Olujobi (2015), done in Ekiti State where the respondents used for the study indicated *Chrysophyllum albidum* (agbalumo), *Irvingia gabonensis* (oro) as forest fruits resources utilized in the study area. This result is also in agreement with Mbani (2015) where various forest fruits such as *Irvingia gabonensis* (oro)bush mango, *Chrysophyllum albidum* (agbalumo), *Garnicia kola*, *Cola acuminata* (*Cola nitida*) as wild fruits resources collected by the rural dwellers. Despite the introduction and widely accepted status of hybrid fruits in the Southwestern part of Nigeria, rural dwellers still values the indigenous/wild fruits which are resources from the forest, hence their commitment to the utilization of the fruits.

For wild vegetable resources utilized across Osun, Ondo and Oyo States, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated they utilize *lactuca taraxacifolia* (yanrin), *senecio biafrae* (woorowo), *struchium sparaganophora* (ewuro odo) and *solanum nigrum* (efo odu). Likewise, 95.6% of the respondents indicated they utilize *Vernonia amygdalina* (ewuro) and *Corchorus olitoris* (ewedu) while 94.1%, 90.9% and 90.6% of the respondents indicated *Amaranthus spinosus* (tete eleeun), *Talinum traingulare* (gbure) and *Capiscum frutescens* as wild vegetable resources they utilized in various forms respectively. Majority (83.5%) of the respondents indicated *Piper nigrum*(ata iyere); 83.2% of the respondents indicated *Telfairia occidentalis*(ugu) while 73.8% of the respondents each indicated *Zingiber officinale* (ata ile) and *Capiscum frutescens* (ata) respectively. Meanwhile, 75.6% of the respondents indicated *Solanum aethiopicum* leaf; 70.3%, 69.4% and 61.8% of the respondents indicated *Abelmoschus esculentus* (Ila), *Momordica balsamina* (ejirin) and *Allium sativum* (ayu) respectively as forest vegetable resources utilized in the study area. The wild vegetables are utilized in various forms and different purposes. Among purposes wild vegetables were utilized as indicated by the respondents includes consuming as food condiments, medicinal purposes in treatment of ailments such as diabetes, ulcer, high blood pressure and likewise the sale of the wild vegetables to urban settlers. This result affirms that wild vegetables are a source of forest sourced livelihood activities for the respondents.

Generally, this result is an indication that rural dwellers utilize indigenous vegetable resources for food and food condiments in the study area. The result is in agreement with the findings of Olujobi (2015), where *Senecio biafrae*, Vegetable (waterleaf), *Abelmoschus esculentus* and pepper were indicated as forest vegetable resources collected by the rural dwellers. This agreed with the reports of Awe *et al.*, (2011), Anel (2006), Jimoh and Haruna (2007), Tee and Amonum (2008) as well as Anon (2000) that rural dwellers gather forest products such as wild vegetables for food and food condiments.

For forest trees resources utilized in the study area, majority (85.0%) and 80.0% of the respondents indicated they utilize *Terminalia superba* and *Milicia spp* while 75.0%, 68.5%, 68.2% and 62.9% of the respondents indicated *Ceiba pentandra*, *Khaya ivorensis* (ogan o), *Triplochiton scleroxylon* (igi arere) and igi agboin respectively as forest trees resources utilized in Southwestern part of Nigeria. Meanwhile, more than half (56.5%) and 50.3% of the respondents indicated *Adansonia digitata* and *Anogeissus leiocarpa* respectively while 46.8% of the

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respondents indicated *Albizia adianthifolia* as utilized forest trees resources in the study area. In addition, 45.0% and 40.9% of the respondents indicated igi ata and *Entandrophragma cylindricum* as utilized forest trees resources in the study area. The forest trees in the study area were utilized for various purposes which includes timber, charcoal production, source of energy, construction of wooden bridges along farm roads and within the community, sale of the tree in form of timber, for house construction, farm implement and branches of trees like *Anogeissus leiocarpa* and igi ata are majorly used as chewing stick for hygienic treatment of the mouth. This result affirms the uniformity of timber species in the Southwestern part of Nigeria, various kinds of species were dominant in the respective States of Ondo, Osun and Oyo. The uniformity of the species in the Southwestern States is connected to the same climatic condition and vegetation experienced in the region. The utilization of the various species of forest tree resources is an assertion that trees as a forest resource are a major contributor to the existence of rural dwellers in the study area in form of income generation and construction of houses/shelter for the populace. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Mbani (2015) that harvested product by rural dwellers in the forest includes timber.

For medicinal plants utilized in the study area, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated they utilize *Azadirachta indica* (ewe igi dongoyaro); 92.4% and 90.6% of the respondents indicated *Azadirachta indicaback* (epo igi dongoyaro) and *Ocimum grattisimum* (efirin) respectively as medicinal forest resource utilized in the study area. Meanwhile, *Morinda lucida* (oruwo), hibiscus (ewe zobo) and *nicotiana tabacum* (ewe taba) were individually indicated by 88.2% of the respondents while 78.8% of the respondents indicated *Xylopiya aethiopica* (eeru) as a medicinal forest resource utilized in the study area. Lastly, 35.0% of the respondents indicated *Azadirachta indicaseed* as forest medicinal plant forest resources utilized in the study area. The medicinal plants were consumed or utilized in various forms whereby some medicinal plants such as *Azadirachta indicaback* (epo igi dongoyaro) were soaked in liquid content such as water, soft drinks (Sprite and 7up) and alcohol (Schnapp). Also, some such as *Ocimum grattisimum* (efirin) were cooked in form of soup for consumption for the treatment of stomach disorderliness and malaria. This study is in line with the research work of Osunderu (2017), where Eeru, Oruwo and Dongoyaro were listed as medicinal plants used in the treatment of disease.

Medicinal plants are important for several reasons. A large proportion of the world's rural population depends on these plants for their health care needs (Largo, 2014). They also provide the basic raw material for the production of traditional medicines (FAO, 2005 and FAO 1987). The collection and processing of medicinal plants provide employment and income opportunities for a large number of people in rural areas (Marshall, Newton and Schreckenber 2003). The importance of traditional medicinal plants in the conservation of biological diversity also merits attention (Okoli, Aigbe, and Ohaju-Obodo) and Mensah, 2007).

Also, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated they utilize *Agaricus bisporuss*, an indication that all rural dwellers in the study area are aware of the quality and nutrients embedded in the consumption of *Agaricus bisporuss*. The result is in line with the result of Mbani (2015) where *Agaricus bisporuss* were indicated by the majority of the respondents. Also, the result agrees with the findings of Olujobi (2015) where the *Agaricus bisporus* was indicated as a widely collected forest resource. Results on utilization of forest *Bambusa vulgaris* as a resource shows that 84.7% indicated they utilize *Bambusa vulgaris* log while 79.4% and 60.0% indicated they utilize *Bambusa vulgaris* leaves and *Bambusa vulgaris* shoots respectively. Meanwhile, 89.4% of the respondents indicated they utilize honey while only 36.3% indicated they utilize fodder and forages. The utilization of honey by the majority of the respondents might be connected to the various medicinal attributes that honey possessed. The result of the finding conforms to the findings of Mbani (2015) as honey was indicated as a major forest resource utilized in the study area.

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For forest sand/building stones utilization as a forest resource, 91.2% of the respondents indicated each of gravel, rock and sharp sand while 85.6% and 80.6% indicated clay soil and soft sand as utilized forest resources. This is an indication that forest sand/building stone plays a significant role as a major asset to the rural dwellers, hence the importance of the forest to the rural dwellers. Rock is used as an agricultural implement in the sun-drying of cassava chips for cassava flour, cashew nut, cocoa amongst other agricultural products that need to be sundried. Also, gravel, sharp sand, soft sand and clay were used in the construction of houses/shelters, yam barns on the farm and sales of these sand/building stones are used for asset formation as indicated by the respondents. Only, 28.5% of the respondents indicated they utilize orchids, an indication that it is not a widely utilized forest resource in the study area.

For bush animals forest resources, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated they utilize *Thryonomys swinderianus* (oya) and *Erethizon dorsatum* (oore) while 95.3% and 94.4% of the respondents indicated *Bovidae* (igala) and *Coturnix Coturnix* (eye aparo) respectively. Moreso, majority (88.2%), 86.2% and 85.9% of the respondents indicated *Numididae* (awo), *Potamochoerus larvatus* (elede Igbo) and *Serpentes* (ejo) respectively. Lastly, 73.5% and 72.9% of the respondents indicated *Cricetomys emini* (okete) and *Varanus* (antaa/aleegba) as forest bush animals resources utilized respectively. Bush animals hunted/collected by the hunters are consumed as meat by the people and also some derived income from the sales of the captured bush animal. It was affirmed by the respondents that the bush animals are consumed and sold off in different forms such as roasted and smoked, used as pepper soup, fried form or sold uncooked as it is displayed along the express road for passerby to purchase from them.

The implication of the high percentage of the respondents indicating the utilization of all available bush meat as a forest resource affirms that bushmeat is still very much available in the forest which is against the assertion that crop farming has eroded the availability of bushmeat in the forest areas. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Onwubuya, Ogbonna and Ezeobiora (2013) that products such as bushmeats were forest products available to rural dwellers. As cited in Ogundele *et al.*, (2012), The Federal Department of Forestry (1987) has noted that wildlife is most highly valued as food and the most commonly consumed species are animals. The survey shows that grass cutters, *Cricetomys eminis* and small *Bovidaes* are the most commonly hunted, consumed and sold animal products in the area, hence the affirmation of the utilization of bush meats in rural dwellers.

Meanwhile, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated they utilize water from the river while 89.1% indicated they utilize leaf (spices and condiment). Water is life; hence the general utilization of water from the river by the rural dwellers affirms the shortage or absence of potable water in the study area, an indication of the absence of government intervention on infrastructural facilities. This supports the findings of Fuwape (2003) that rural dwellers engaged in the collection and marketing of forest tree leaves.

For resources obtained from coconut/palm tree as a forest resource, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated they utilize palm oil while 90.9% of the respondents indicated palm tree log as forest coconut/palm tree resources utilized in the study area. this result affirms the importance attached to the palm tree in the daily lives of the rural dwellers. The utilization of palm oil by the rural dwellers have a direct effect on the consumption pattern of urban people of palm oil, as palm oil is a major condiment used for cooking in the Southwest zone of Nigeria. Majority (86.2%), 85.3% and 82.1% of the respondents indicated they utilize coconut tree logs, palm nut and coconut fruit respectively while 71.8% of the respondents indicated coconut fruit chaff as forest coconut/palm tree produces and products utilized respectively. Coconut tree logs, palm tree logs are sold as timbers for house construction, though when dried they are seldomly used as a source of energy. Also, palm oil is consumed majorly as cooking ingredients while women are especially

engaged in the sale of palm oil as income-generating activities. Lastly, 60.6% of the respondents indicated palm leaves as forest resources utilized in the study area. Palm leaves are used as roofing materials for huts built on the farm, used as raw materials for the production of brooms and weaving materials while some respondents who are farmers indicated they make use of the palm fronds/ leaves for spraying of chemicals on their plants in the absence of knapsack sprayers.

According to the findings of Mbani (2015), oil palm products were harvested and used for various purposes including as construction materials for the roofing of houses, huts, the building of local bridges across small streams and staking of farm crops; fibre for lightening, heating, making ropes, fishing nets, broom for keeping the house and environment clean and basket for preserving food items; cosmetics (soap and body oil) and wine and spirit for relaxation and entertaining visitors. This could be the reason Anel (2006) stated that life would be virtually impossible for most people living in rural areas of developing countries, including Nigeria, without the availability of palm leaves for roofing as many people in these regions have no money to buy zinc sheets for roofing.

The result revealed in Table 4.8 shows that 88.2% and 79.1% of the rural dwellers utilize firewood and *Gastropods* respectively. This result is in line with the findings of Mbani (2015), where the majority (68.5%) of the rural dwellers used fuelwood as a source of energy for cooking. Also, the result is similar to Inoni (2009) who reported that fuelwood supplied 78.2% of the total energy requirements of rural poor dwellers for cooking and heating. Aside, the consumption of *Gastropods* as condiments for food and as food, the *Gastropods* are utilized for medicinal purposes to treat various diseases and many other infirmities.

Generally, this result affirmed that forest resources available in the study area are utilized though the resources are utilized based on the availability of forest resources in the study area and the demand for use in the rural dwellers. As cited in Ogundele *et al.*, (2012), Adedayo and Akindele (2003) maintained that forests are a common property resource that plays a crucial role in rural livelihood. These products are also potential pillars of sustainable forestry hence the reason behind the utilization of the forest resources in the study area.

Forms of Utilization of Forest Resources

In line with the distribution of results in Table 3, various forms of utilization of harvested forest resources were identified by the respondents. For fruits forest resources, all (100.0%) the respondents indicated that *chrysophyllum albidum* (agbalumo) and guava, 87.6% indicated that *Irvingiagabonensis* (oro), bush mango (70.69%), lime (83.5%), avocado pear (56.5%), tiger nut (ofi ho) (36.8%), bitter kola (orogbo) (95.9%), kolanut (obi) (85.9%) and garden egg (95.9%) are consumed in its raw form by the respondents. Also, *treculia africana* (African breadfruit) (90.3%), *Irvingiagabonensis* (oro) (12.4%), lime and walnut (asala) (94.4%) avocado pear (77.4%) and garden egg (igba) (73.5%) indicated that they consumed the aforementioned forest resources in cooked form. In addition, the respondents indicated that they realized income from *chrysophyllum albidum* (agbalumo) (36.2%), *treculia africana* (African breadfruit) (19.1%), *Irvingiagabonensis* (oro) (71.5%), lime (osan wewe) (75.3%), walnut (asala) (80.9%), avocado pear (67.6%), bitter kola (orogbo) (95.9%), kola nut (obi) (77.6%) and garden egg (igba) (46.8%).

For vegetables forest resources, it was indicated that 90.6% of the respondents indicated that bitter leaf (ewuro), pumpkin (63.2%), ginger (ata ile) (35.9%), turmeric (ata ile pupa) (4.1%), balsam pear (ejirin) (37.4) and garlic (ayu) (36.7%) were consumed raw while 79.1% indicated bitter leaf (ewuro), jute leaf (ewedu) (100.0%), water leaf (gbure) (79.1%), pumpkin (ugu) (79.1%), okra (ila) (75.6%) were consumed cooked, ginger (ata ile) (85.9%), turmeric (ata ile pupa) (61.5%), black pepper (ata iyere) (42.4%), thorny pigweed (tete eleegun) and balsam pear (ejirin) (63.2%), garlic (ayu) (75.6%), Tabasco pepper (ata), latuca *taraxacifolia*, *senecio biafrae* (woorowo), *struchium sparaganophora* (ewuro odo) and

solanum nigrum (efo odu) (68.2%) as vegetable forest resources consumed cooked. Also, 95.9% of the respondents indicated that they consumed leaf (spices and condiment) when cooked while garden egg leaf (ewe igba) was indicated by all (100.0%) as vegetables consumed in its cooked form.

Meanwhile, bitter leaf (ewuro) (86.5%), pumpkin (ugu) (83.2%), ginger (ata ile) and turmeric (ata ile pupa) (56.2%), balsam pear (ejirin) (77.1%) and garlic (ayu) (58.2%) indicated that they were consumed for medicinal purpose in the dwellers. For tree forest resources, igi iroko (55.9%), mahogany (50.3%), obeche (44.1%), igi ayin (53.2%), igi afara (52.6%), igi ata (34.1%), igi agboin (36.4%), igi araba (30.0%), igi ayunre (30.3%), igi oomo (49.1%) and igi sapele (43.2%) were indicated by the respondents that they were used for agricultural input; igi iroko (81.8%), mahogany (69.7%), obeche (77.6%), igi ayin (74.1%), igi afara (54.4%), igi ata (44.7%), igi agboin (31.2%), igi araba (44.4%), igi ayunre (37.9%), igi oomo (38.2%) and igi sapele (22.9%) were indicated by the respondents that they were used asset formation; igi iroko and mahogany (28.8%), obeche (49.7%), igi ayin (32.1%), igi afara (36.2%), igi ata (22.9%), igi agboin (39.4%), igi araba (12.1%), igi ayunre (13.5%), igi oomo (10.0%) and igi sapele (32.4%) were indicated by the respondents that they were used as source of energy while igi iroko (25.0%), mahogany (20.2%), obeche (20.0%), igi ayin (19.4%), igi afara (22.1%), igi ata (18.5%), igi agboin (21.8%), igi araba (17.4%), igi ayunre (31.2%), igi oomo (29.4%) and igi sapele (20.5%) indicated they realized income from collection of these forest resources.

For medicinal plants, neem tree back (epo igi) (63.2%), neem leaf (ewe dongoyaro) (100.0%), neem seed (4.1%), basil (efirin) (100.0%), brimstone (oruwo) (90.0%) and hibiscus (ewe zobo) (100.0%) and negro pepper (eeru) (61.2%) were cooked before consumed for curing of ailments; neem tree back (epo igi) (59.7%), neem leaf (ewe dongoyaro) (100.0%), neem seed (40.3%), basil (efirin) (81.8%), brimstone (oruwo) (81.8%), hibiscus (ewe zobo) (25.6%), nicotiana tabacum (ewe taba) (32.6%) and negro pepper (eeru) (65.6%) were processed before consumed for medicinal purpose; 95.9% indicated that nicotiana tabacum (ewe taba) is used as indigenous symbol for prevention of snakes.

For bamboo forest resources, 43.8% indicated that bamboo leaves are used as agricultural inputs while 20.9% indicated that bamboo leaves were used as asset formation. Also, 86.5% and 96.5% of the respondents indicated bamboo log was utilized as agricultural input and asset formation respectively. Also, 88.8% and 90.6% indicated that bamboo log was used as a source of energy and as a source of income respectively.

For forest sand/building stones, 66.8% of the respondents indicated that rock is used as agricultural input where it is used to sun dry cassava flour; 90.05% of the respondents indicated that gravel, rock and soft sand were utilized for asset formation while 86.5% and 60.9% indicated sharp sand and clay soil as resources utilized for asset formation. For economic return from the forest resources, gravel (80.0%), rock (46.2%), sharp sand and soft sand (59.1%) while 61.8% indicated clay soil as forest resources sold to generate income for the rural dwellers in the study area.

For bush meat forest resources, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated that they consumed cooked grasscutter (oya), 89.1% indicated porcupine (oore), 80.0% indicated bush pig (elede igbo), antelope (igala) and giant rat (okete), 59.1% indicated monitor lizard (antaa/alegbe) and snakes, quail (eiye aparo) 80.0% while 70. % and 89.1% indicated guinea fowl (awo) and snails as bush meat they consumed in the study area respectively. Also, 90.6% indicated grasscutter (90.6%), all (100.0%) the respondents indicated from porcupine (oore), bush pig (elede igbo) and antelope (igala), giant rat (okete) (79.1%), monitor lizard (antaa/alegbe) and snakes (ejo) (100.0%), quail (eiye aparo) (79.1%), guinea fowl (awo) (100.0%) and snails (57.4%) as bush meat they realized income from to sustain their livelihood status in the study area. Also, 66.2% indicated that snails are utilized for medicinal purposes while 22.4% utilized them as a symbol for traditional purposes.

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For coconut/palm tree forest resources, 83.5% and 21.5% indicated they consume coconut fruit and palm wine raw while all (100.0%) indicated that palm oil is consumed cooked. Meanwhile, 63.2% indicated palm tree log while 69.7% indicated coconut tree log as agricultural input; 9.4%, 72.4% and 96.5% indicated that palm leaves, palm tree log and coconut tree log were utilized as asset formation; 57.9% indicated that palm nut was processed while 79.1% indicated that palm wine is used for medicinal purpose. Furthermore, 63.8% indicated that palm tree log and 75.0% indicated that coconut tree logs was used as a source of energy while 55.9% indicated that coconut fruit chaff is also utilized as a source of energy. Palm wine (34.1%), palm oil (60.9%) and palm nut (67.9%), palm tree log (68.8%), coconut fruit (54.1%) and coconut tree log (55.9%) were all indicated as forest resources they derived income from in the study area.

Meanwhile, all (100.0%) of the respondents indicated water/river are utilized as agricultural input and for dwellers use while 52.6% engage in the practice of fetching water for people to raise income. Also, 66.2% consumes honey in the raw form, all (100.0%) utilize it for medicinal purpose, 67.9% utilizes honey for traditional/religious purpose while 60.6% indicated they engage in the sales of honey. Lastly, 80.9% indicated that firewood is utilized as a source of energy while 66.8% indicated that income is derived from the sales of firewood.

Generally, this result is an indication that forest resources serve various purpose to the rural dwellers and the sale is an indication that urban settlers also utilize forest resources for their daily activities, though their utilization has much more financial implication on them than the rural dwellers who live next to the forest areas. The sale of the forest resources is an affirmation of the fact that forest resources are a major contributor to the economy of the Southwest and Nigeria as a whole, as processing industries such as saw millers, paper making industries amongst others utilize forest resources as their major raw materials.

The various forms at which the forest resource is utilized create job opportunity for the rural dwellers as they rely on the forest product for their source of income most especially the vulnerable ones who majorly engages in the sale of snails, indigenous vegetables, fetching of water to raise income amongst other economic opportunities that are characterized with less or no financial implication. This result is in line with the findings of Mbani (2015) where various harvested forest resources are utilized in various forms such as food, source of income, medicinal, construction, source of energy amongst others. This agreed with the reports of Awe *et al.* (2011), Aniel (2006), Jimoh and Haruna (2007), Tee and Amonum (2008) as well as Anon (2000) that rural dwellers gather forest products for food and food condiments. The importance of the various forms of utilization of forest resources in the study area affirms the position of Aniel (2006) who stated that life would be virtually impossible for most people living in rural areas of developing countries, including Nigeria, without the availability of palm leaves for roofing as many people in these regions have no money to buy zinc sheets for roofing.

Constraints to Utilization of Forest Resources

Table 4 reveals the constraints encountered by the rural dwellers in Southwestern zone of Nigeria. Analysis of constraints faced by rural dwellers in utilizing forest resources in the Southwest part of Nigeria revealed that they were constrained by the following; lack of extension contact to promote knowledge on use of the forest resources, deforestation, restriction of access to forest area by government, religious and cultural belief bias towards utilization of herbs and concoction, lack of modern storage facilities, easy perishability of harvested forest resources, low market value for forest resources, high cost of transportation to market destination, fear of attack by wild forest animals, problem of insect and disease infestation, extinction of plant species through uncontrolled/unsupervised bush burning and extinction of animal species through uncontrolled/unsupervised bush burning.

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Furthermore, the rural dwellers ranked deforestation, lack of extension contact to promote knowledge on use of the forest resources, lack of modern storage facilities and high cost of transportation to market destination with weighted mean score of 2.6, 2.5 and 2.4 respectively as the very severe constraints encountered, this was followed by easy perishability of harvested forest resources, low market value for forest resources, extinction of plant species through uncontrolled/unsupervised bush burning and extinction of animal species through uncontrolled/unsupervised bush burning with weighted mean scores of 2.1, 1.8 and 1.7 respectively. Furthermore, restriction of access to forest area by government, problem of insect and disease infestation, fear of attack by wild forest animals and religious and cultural belief bias towards utilization of herbs and concoction with weighted mean scores of 1.0, 0.9, 0.6 and 0.5 respectively were also indicated as constraints.

The importance and effects of forest resources utilization to rural dwellers in terms of economy, health, social and the rural livelihood cannot be overemphasized; hence efforts should be made to curtail the constraints encountered. Despite the contribution of the forest resources to the rural dwellers, a number of factors constitute hindrances to the effective utilization of forest products. These constraints are majorly linked with the inefficiency of the governments as provision of social infrastructure could limit the effects of the constraints if at all there would be any. This finding is similar with the result of Mbani (2015), where deforestation and lack of extension contact were ranked 1st and 2nd as the major constraints facing rural dwellers utilization of forest resources in Enugu State of the South-East part of Nigeria. Also, this result is in tandem with the findings of Nzeh *et al.*, (2015), Eneje *et al.*, (2013) and Babalola (2009) that lack of modern technology for processing and storage of forest products, deforestation, poor means of transportation, insect and pest disease, bush burning, and deterioration/perishability among others are problems to utilization and marketing of forest resources. This study affirms the consistency of the constraints faced in the utilization of forest resources as the findings reveals similar reports with the findings of World Health Organization (WHO) (2004), reported that losses in forest fruits and vegetables occur as a result of poor means of transportation, lack of storage facilities and refrigeration.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concluded that forest resources are available in the Southwest region of Nigeria and it was established that forest based rural people utilizes the available forest resources in the study area though through various form ranging from consumption, agricultural input, medicine, source of energy and for economic purpose amongst other several forms. Deforestation, lack of extension contact to promote knowledge on use of the forest resources, lack of modern storage facilities and high cost of transportation to market destination were accorded highest ranking order to constraints to the utilization of forest resources by the respondents. Based on the result gathered, it is recommended that there is a need for concerned agencies, stakeholders and governments to employ environmental extension specialists with competence in environmental resources to aid the promotion and increase the awareness of the people on various beneficial attributes to derive from the utilization of forests.

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Table 1 Distribution of Respondents according to their Socio-Economic Characteristics

Socio-Economic Characteristics	*Frequency	Percentages	Mean
Sex			
Male	185	54.4	
Female	155	45.6	
Age			
≤30	27	7.9	
31-40	31	9.1	51.0
41-50	117	34.4	
51-60	45	13.2	
Above 60	120	35.3	
Household size			
≤ 5	104	30.6	7.0
6-10	197	57.9	
Above 10	39	11.5	
Years spent in school			
No formal education	28	8.2	
≤ 6	54	15.9	10.0

7-12	195	57.4		
Above 12	63	18.5		
Marital status				
Single	37	10.9		
Married	192	56.5		
Widow	74	21.8		
Divorced	20	5.9		
Separated	17	5.0		
Income from forest collection (₦)				
≤100,000	154	45.3		
101,000-200,000	81	23.8		
201,000-300,000	40	11.8		
Above 300,000	65	19.1		
Farm size (ha)				
< 4	115	60.8		
5-8	74	39.2	4.42	1.79
Ethnic group				
Yoruba	185	97.9		
Igbo	4	2.1		

Source: Field survey, 2023 **S.D:** Standard deviation

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Table 2 Distribution of respondents according to forest resources utilized in
n=340

Southwest Nigeria

S/N	Forest resources	Utilized forest resources	
		*Frequency	Percentage
1	Fruits		
	<i>Chrysophyllum albidum</i> (agbalumo)	294	86.5
	<i>Treculia africana</i> (African breadfruit)	258	75.9
	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i> Bush Mango (Oro)	274	80.6
	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	240	70.6
	<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i>	296	87.1
	<i>Juglans regia</i> (Asala)	276	81.2
	<i>Persea americana</i>	290	85.3
	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i> (Ofi ho)	89	26.2
	<i>Garnicia kola</i> (Orogbo)	250	73.5
	<i>Cola acuminata</i> (Obi)	254	74.7
	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i> (Igba)	305	89.7
2	Vegetables		
	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> (Ewuro)	325	95.6
	<i>Corchorus olitoris</i> (Ewedu)	325	95.6
	<i>Talinum triangulare</i> (Gbure)	309	90.9
	<i>Telfairia occidentalis</i> (Ugu)	283	83.2
	<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i> (Ila)	239	70.3
	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Ata ile)	251	73.8
	<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Ata ile pupa)	251	73.8
	<i>Piper nigrum</i> (Ata Iyere)	284	83.5
	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> (Tete Eleegun)	320	94.1
	<i>Momordica balsamina</i> (Ejirin)	236	69.4
	<i>Allium sativum</i> (Ayu)	210	61.8
	<i>Capiscum frutescens</i> (ata)	308	90.6
	<i>Lactuca taraxacifolia</i> (Yanrin)	340	100.0
	<i>Senecio biafrae</i> (Woorowo)	340	100.0
		340	100.0

	<i>Struchium sparaganophora</i> (Ewuro odo)	340	100.0
	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> (Efo odu)	257	75.6
	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i> leaf (Ewe igba)		
3	Timber		
	<i>Milicia spp</i>	272	80.0
	<i>Khaya ivorensis</i>	233	68.5
	<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i>	232	68.2
	<i>Anogeissus leiocarpa</i>	171	50.3
	<i>Terminalia superba</i>	289	85.0
	Igi ata	153	45.0
	Igi agboin	214	62.9
	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	255	75.0
	<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	159	46.8
	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	192	56.5
	<i>Entandrophragma cylindricum</i>	139	40.9
4	Medicinal plants		
	<i>Azadirachta indicaback</i> (Epo igi)	314	92.4
	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Ewe dongoyaro)	340	100.0
	<i>Azadirachta indicaseed</i>	119	35.0
	<i>Ocimum grattisimum</i> (Efirin)	308	90.6
	<i>Morinda lucida</i> (Oruwo)	300	88.2
	Hibiscus (Ewe zobo)	300	88.2
	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> (Ewe taba)	300	88.2
	<i>Xylopi aethiopica</i> (Eeru)	268	78.8
5	<i>Agaricus bisporus</i> (Olu)	340	100.0
6	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>		
	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> shoots	204	60.0
	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> leaves	270	79.4
	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> log	288	84.7
7	Fodder and forages	124	36.5
8	Honey	304	89.4

9	Forest sand/building stones		
	Gravel	310	91.2
	Rock	310	91.2
	Sharp sand	310	91.2
	Soft sand	274	80.6
	Clay soil	291	85.6
10	Orchids	97	28.5
11	Bush meat		
	<i>Thryonomys swinderianus</i> (Oya)	340	100.0
	<i>Erethizon dorsatum</i> (Oore)	340	100.0
	<i>Potamochoerus larvatus</i> (Elede igbo)	293	86.2
	<i>Bovidae</i> (Igalala)	324	95.3
	<i>Cricetomys emini</i> (Okete)	250	73.5
	<i>Varanus</i> (Antaa/Aleegba)	248	72.9
	<i>Serpentes</i> (Ejo)	292	85.9
	<i>Coturnix Coturnix</i> (Eiye aparo)	321	94.4
	<i>Numididae</i> (Awo)	300	88.2
12	Leaf (spices and condiment)	303	89.1
13	Water/river	340	100.0
14	Coconut/Palm tree		
	Palm wine	202	59.4
	Palm oil	340	100.0
	Palm nut	290	85.3
	Palm leaves	206	60.6
	Palm tree Log	309	90.9
	Coconut fruit	279	82.1
	Coconut tree Log	293	86.2
	Coconut fruit chaff	244	71.8
15	Snails	269	79.1
16	Firewood	300	88.2

Source: Field survey, 2023

*: Multiple responses

Table 3 Distribution of respondents according to forms of utilization of collected forest resources in Southwest States of Nigeria

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S/N	Forest resources	CSM Raw F (%)	CSM Cooked F (%)	AI F (%)	AF F (%)	PRO F (%)	MD F (%)	SYM F (%)	ENERGY F (%)	SALE F (%)
1	Fruits									
	<i>Chrysophyllum albidum</i> (agbalumo)	340 (100.0)	-							123 (36.2)
	<i>Treculia africana</i> (African breadfruit)									
	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i> Bush mango (Oro)	-	307 (90.3)							65 (19.1)
	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	298 (87.6)	42 (12.4)							243 (71.5)
	<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i>	340 (100.0)	-							
	<i>Juglans regia</i> (Asala)	284 (83.5)	321 (94.4)							256 (75.3)
	<i>Persea americana</i>	-	321 (94.4)							275 (80.9)
	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i> (Ofi ho)	192 (56.5)	263 (77.4)							230 (67.6)
	<i>Garcinia kola</i> (Orogbo)	125 (36.8)	-							-
	<i>Cola acuminata</i> (Obi)	326 (95.9)	-							326 (95.9)
	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i> (Igba)	292 (85.9)	-							264 (77.6)
		326 (95.9)	256 (73.5)							159 (46.8)

2	Vegetables			
	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> (Ewuro)	308 (90.6)	269 (79.1)	244 (86.5)
		-	340 (100.0)	
	<i>Corchorus olitoris</i> (Ewedu)	-	269 (79.1)	
	<i>Talinum traingulare</i> (Gbure)	215 (63.2)	269 (79.1)	283 (83.2)
		-	257 (75.6)	
	<i>Telfairia occidentalis</i> (Ugu)	122 (35.9)	292 (88.9)	
	<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i> (Ila)	14 (4.1)	209 (61.5)	191 (56.2)
		-	144(42.4)	
	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Ata ile)	-	215 (63.2)	191 (56.2)
		-	215 (63.2)	
	<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Ata ile pupa)	127 (37.4)	215 (63.2)	
	<i>Piper nigrum</i> (Ata Iyere)	189 (55.6)	257 (75.6)	
			232 (68.2)	
	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> (Tete Eleegun)			262 (72.1)
	<i>Momordica balsamina</i> (Ejirin)	-	232 (68.2)	198 (58.2)
		-	232 (68.2)	
	<i>Allium sativum</i> (Ayu)			

<i>Capiscum frutescens</i> (ata)	-	232 (68.2)			
	-	232 (68.2)			
<i>Lactuca taraxacifolia</i> (Yanrin)	-	340 (100.0)			
<i>Senecio biafrae</i> (Woorowo)	-	326 (95.9)			75 (22.1)
	-	340 (100.0)			181 (53.2)
<i>Struchium</i> <i>sparaganophora</i> (Ewuro odo)					
<i>Solanum nigrum</i> (Efo odu)				326 (95.9)	
<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i> leaf (Ewe igba)					
Leaf spices and condiment					
<i>Agaricus bisporus</i>					
3 Trees					
<i>Milicia spp</i>		190 (55.9)	278 (81.8)		98 (28.8) 85 (25.0)
<i>Khaya ivorensis</i>		171 (50.3)	234 (69.7)		98 (28.8) 69 (20.2)
<i>Triplochition</i> <i>scleroxylon</i>		150 (44.1)	264 (77.6)		169 (49.7) 68 (20.0)
<i>Anogeissus leiocarpa</i>		181 (53.2)	252 (74.1)		109 (32.1) 66 (19.4)

<i>Terminalia superba</i>		179 (52.6)	185 (54.4)		123 (36.2)	75 (22.1)
Igi ata		116 (34.1)	152 (44.7)		78 (22.9)	63 (18.5)
Igi agboin		131 (36.4)	106 (31.2)		134 (39.4)	74 (21.8)
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>		102 (30.0)	151 (44.4)		41 (12.1)	59 (17.4)
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>		103 (30.3)	129 (37.9)		46 (13.5)	106 (31.2)
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>		167 (49.1)	130 (38.2)		34 (10.0)	100 (29.4)
<i>Entandrophragma cylindricum</i>		147 (43.2)	78 (22.9)		110 (32.4)	70 (20.5)
4 Medicinal plants						
<i>Azadirachta indicaback</i> (Epo igi)	-	88 (63.3)		203 (59.7)		
	-	139 (100.0)		340 (100.0)		
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Ewe dongoyaro)	-	4 (2.9)		137 (40.3)		
<i>Azadirachta indicaseed</i>	-	139 (100.0)		278 (81.8)		
<i>Ocimum grattisimum</i> (Efirin)	-	123 (88.5)		278 (81.8)		
	-	139 (100.0)		87 (25.6)		
<i>Morinda lucida</i> (Oruwo)						
Hibiscus (Ewe zobo)	-				326	
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> (Ewe taba)	-	55 (39.6)		111 (32.6)	326 (95.9)	
				223 (65.6)		

	<i>Xylopiya aethiopica</i> (Eeru)				
5	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>				
	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> shoots	-			
		149 (43.8)	71 (20.9)		
	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> leaves	294 (86.5)	328 (96.5)	302 (88.8)	308 (90.6)
	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> log				
6	Forest sand/building stones				
			306 (90.0)		272 (80.0)
	Gravel	227 (66.8)	306 (90.0)		157 (46.2)
	Rock		294 (86.5)		201 (59.1)
	Sharp sand		306 (90.0)		201 (59.1)
	Soft sand		207 (60.9)	158 (46.5)	210 (61.8)
	Clay soil				
7	Bush animals				
	<i>Thryonomys</i> <i>swinderianus</i> (Oya)	340 (100.0)			308 (90.6)
		303 (89.1)			340 (100.0)
	<i>Erethizon dorsatum</i> (Oore)	272 (80.0)			340 (100.0)
		272 (80.0)			340 (100.0)

<i>Potamochoerus larvatus</i> (Elede igbo)	272 (80.0)							269 (79.1)
<i>Bovidae</i> (Igala)	201 (59.1)							340 (100.0)
<i>Cricetomys emini</i> (Okete)	201 (59.1)							340 (100.0)
<i>Varanus</i> (Antaa/Aleegba)	272 (80.0)				84 (60.4)			269 (79.1)
	238 (70.0)							340 (100.0)
<i>Serpentes</i> (Ejo)	327 (96.2)					225 (66.2)	76 (22.4)	195 (57.4)
<i>Coturnix Coturnix</i> (Eiye aparo)								
<i>Numididae</i> (Awo)								
<i>Gastropods</i>								
8 Coconut/Palm tree								
Palm wine	73 (21.5)	-	-	-	-	269 (79.1)		116 (34.1)
Palm oil	-	340 (100.0)	-	-	-		79 (23.2)	207 (60.9)
Palm nut	-	-	-		197 (57.9)			231 (67.9)
Palm leaves	-	-	66 (19.4)	32 (9.4)	-			-
Palm tree Log	-	-	215 (63.2)	246 (72.4)	-		217 (63.8)	234 (68.8)
Coconut fruit	284 (83.5)	-	-	-	-		-	184 (54.1)
Coconut tree Log	-	-	237 (69.7)	328 (96.5)	-		257 (75.6)	190 (55.9)

Coconut fruit chaff	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9 Other forest resources							
Water/river			340 (100.0)				179 (52.6)
Honey	225 (66.2)				340 (100.0)	231 (67.9)	206 (60.6)
Firewood						275 (80.9)	227 (66.8)
Fodder and forages							
Orchids			99 (29.1)				

KEY: CSM- Consumption, ED- Edible (raw), NE- Non edible (cooked), AI- Agricultural input, AF- Asset formation, PRO- Processed, MD- Medicine, SYM- Symbolic, ENE- Energy

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 4 Constraints encountered in utilization of forest resources in Southwestern State of Nigeria

S/N	Constraints	Very severe F (%)	Severe F (%)	Mild Severe F (%)	Not Severe F (%)	WMS	Rank
1	Lack of extension contact to promote knowledge on use of the forest resources	177 (52.1)	163 (47.9)	-	-	2.5	2 nd
2	Deforestation	191 (56.2)	149 (43.8)	-	-	2.6	1 st
3	Restriction of access to forest area by government	26 (7.6)	74 (21.8)	100 (29.4)	140 (41.2)	1.0	9 th
4	Religious and cultural beliefs bias towards utilization of herbs and concoction	26 (7.6)	-	106 (31.2)	208 (61.2)	0.5	12 th
5	Lack of modern storage facilities	177 (52.1)	149 (43.8)	-	14 (4.1)	2.4	3 rd
6	Easy perishability of harvested forest resources	65 (19.1)	261 (76.8)	-	14 (4.1)	2.1	5 th

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7	Low market value for forest resources	121 (35.6)	116 (34.1)	31 (9.1)	72 (21.2)	1.8	6 th
8	High cost of transportation to market destination	138 (40.6)	202 (59.4)	-	-	2.4	3 rd
9	Fear of attack by wild forest animal	19 (5.6)	74 (21.8)	-	247 (72.6)	0.6	11 th
10	Problem of insect and disease infestation	-	93 (27.4)	113 (33.2)	134 (39.4)	0.9	10 th
11	Extinction of plant species through uncontrolled/unsupervised bush burning	31 (9.1)	189 (55.6)	120 (35.3)	-	1.7	7 th
12	Extinction of animal species through uncontrolled/unsupervised bush burning	12 (3.5)	242 (71.2)	54 (15.9)	32 (9.4)	1.7	7 th

Source: Field survey, 2023

F: Frequency

%: Percentage

WMS: Weighted mean score